

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

ELEKTROKİMYƏVİ TƏDQİQATLA BİTUMLU MATERIALLARIN TURŞ QUDRONDAN ALINMASI

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AN ELECTROCHEMICAL STUDY ON OBTAINING BITUMINOUS MATERIALS FROM ACID TAR

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Turşu qətranından elektrokimyəvi üsulla bitumlu materialların alınması prosesi elektrokimyəvi elementin köməyi ilə turşu qətranını onun tərkib hissələrinə parçalamaqdan ibarətdir, daha sonra bitumlu materialları almaq üçün ayrılıb təmizləmə bilər. Turşu qətranı əvvəlcə uyğun elektrolitlə qarışdırılır və elektrokimyəvi elementin anod bölməsinə daxil edilir. Hüceyrədən cərəyan keçir, turşu qətranının elektrolizinə səbəb olur, nəticədə hidrogen qazı və bitumlu materialların qarışığı və digər əlavə məhsullar əmələ gəlir. Bitumlu materiallar daha sonra distillə, həlledicinin çıxarılması və filtrasiya daxil ola biləcək bir sıra təmizləmə mərhələlərindən istifadə etməklə əlavə məhsullardan ayrılıb bilər. Nəticədə əldə edilən bitumlu materiallar müxtəlif tətbiqlər üçün, o cümlədən asfalt və səki tikintisində bağlayıcı kimi istifadə edilə bilər. Elektrokimyəvi üsul turşu qətranından bitumlu materialların əldə edilməsinin ənənəvi üsulları ilə müqayisədə bir sıra üstünlüklər təklif edir, o cümlədən daha yüksək effektivlik, azaldılmış tullantı və məhsulun təmizliyi. Bununla belə, proses mürəkkəb ola bilər və xüsusi avadanlıq və təcrübə tələb edə bilər. Turşu qətranının atılması texnikasının seçiminə yağıntılar (qar, yağış) nəticəsində zamanla dəyişən tullantıların xüsusiyyətləri böyük təsir göstərir.

Abstract

Obtaining bituminous materials from acid tar using an electrochemical process involves the utilization of an electrochemical cell to disintegrate the acid tar into its component parts, allowing for the isolation and refinement of bituminous materials through subsequent purification processes. Initially, the acid tar is combined with an appropriate electrolyte and introduced into the anode chamber of an electrochemical cell. Upon the passage of a current through the cell, the acid tar undergoes electrolysis, leading to the generation of hydrogen gas and a blend of bituminous substances, as well as other secondary products. The bituminous materials can then be separated from the by-products using a series of purification steps, which may include distillation, solvent extraction, and filtration. The resulting bituminous materials can be used for a variety of applications, including as binders in asphalt and pavement construction.

The electrochemical method offers several advantages over traditional methods of obtaining bituminous materials from acid tar, including greater efficiency, reduced waste, and improved product purity. However, the process can be complex and may require specialized equipment and expertise.

The choice of acid resin disposal technique is greatly influenced by the properties of waste that change over time as a result of precipitation (snow, rain).

Açar sözlər: bitumlu materiallar, elektrokimyəvi üsul, turşu qətranı, turşu qətranının utilizasiyası texnikası.

Keywords: bituminous materials, electrochemical method, acid tar, acid resin disposal technique.

INTRODUCTION

In the past, the standard practice for disposing of acid tars, which are hazardous waste materials, was to drain them and store them in specialized outdoor ponds or artificial earthen structures. However, with the advancements in sulfur-acid oil purification technologies in the major industries, this method is no longer necessary. The refining and petrochemical sectors generate significant quantities of acid tars as waste during the process of converting oil into commercial products, particularly when purifying medical, cosmetic, perfume, petroleum oils, paraffins, and high-quality motor fuels using sulfuric acid. The properties and structure

of acid tars vary and change over time due to reactions between organic components, sulfuric acid, atmospheric oxygen, and climate conditions. It is essential to understand the composition and properties of acid tars to identify the suitable technology for processing the waste and the qualities of the resulting products. These factors must be considered when selecting the appropriate technology for utilizing acid tars.

Acid tar (AT) - are environmental pain for far abroad countries. In particular, in Hungary, Brazil, and Mexico, hundreds of thousands of tons of these wastes are concentrated in storage ponds, which, according to the classification, have a second hazard class. And now,

although in smaller quantities, these "reserves" continue to be replenished, which determines the significant need for the need for such studies that will allow the processing of Acid tar (AT) into marketable products.

Understanding the properties and structure of Acid tar (AT) is essential to identify the appropriate technology for processing the waste and to determine the qualities of the resulting products. The composition of Acid tar (AT) in storage ponds is not constant and changes over time due to various chemical reactions that take place between organic components, sulfuric acid, atmospheric oxygen, and weather conditions. Factors such as rain and snow can also affect the properties of Acid tar (AT) in storage ponds. These changing properties need to be considered when selecting the appropriate technology for utilizing Acid tar (AT) waste. Storage ponds typically have three layers: the top layer consists of acid oil, which is the lighter oily portion of the Acid tar (AT) that has already undergone processing; the middle layer is acidic water, which is made up of atmospheric precipitation, sulfuric acid, and acid sulfonated tars and is sent for neutralization in the facility's water treatment system; and the bottom layer comprises pasty bottom acid sludge, which is not currently disposed of. A significant influence on the choice of technology for the utilization of acid tars is exerted by the time-varying properties of the waste due to the effects of precipitation (snow, rain), in addition, the contents of storage ponds are divided into three layers:

- top - acid oil (light oily part of acid tar), at the moment this layer has been worked out;
- medium - acidic water, consisting of atmospheric precipitation, sulfuric acid and acid sulfonated tars, this layer is sent for neutralization to the factory water treatment system;
- lower - bottom acid sludge (pasty state), currently not disposed of.

At present, considerable material has been accumulated on methods for utilizing acid tars, but all the proposed technologies usually come down to burning them in a mixture with carbon-containing fuel or hydrogen sulfide to produce sulfur dioxide.

Numerous studies have been devoted to the issues of increasing the efficiency of Acid tar (AT) processing. In the papers, the methods of high-temperature (800...1200°C) thermal decomposition of Acid tar (AT) and low-temperature (160...350°C) methods are considered, the effect of temperature on Acid tar (AT) with coke production is estimated. But as a result of this process, the strongest coke formation occurs and the cleaning of the tube space of the heat exchanger is costly, in addition, heating the coolant also requires significant energy costs, so this scheme is not used now. There is a method of two-stage coking of Acid tar (AT) with a liquid organic coolant to produce high-sulfur coke, as well as processes of low-temperature reduction of Acid tar (AT) with hydrocarbon residues from oil refining, distillation residues from synthetic fatty acids, and pine tar. The main reason why these methods do not find industrial application is the lack of marketing of high sulfur coke, as well as high sulfur liquid products. In addition, a significant disadvantage of these processes is the

severe corrosion of individual apparatuses, the difficulty of heating and transporting a solid coolant.

All of these factors require the development of non-standard solutions in the process of processing, disposal of Acid tar (AT). To date, no effective integrated method has been proposed for processing all the components of Acid tar (AT) (organic mass, sulfonic acids, sulfuric acid) into specific commercial products, or for recycling Acid tar (AT) into an environmentally friendly material.

In the oil refining and petrochemical industries, technological processes based on the use of sulfuric acid as a reagent or catalyst are widely used. This produces a significant amount of unwanted production waste - spent sulfuric acid and acid tars. Due to the difficulty of disposing of these wastes in the oil refining industry, there is a tendency to reduce the consumption of sulfuric acid. [15]

Acid tars are considered hazardous waste due to their high viscosity and the presence of organic compounds, free sulfuric acid, and water. These waste products are generated during the purification and sulfonation processes of various petroleum products and individual hydrocarbons using sulfuric acid, oleum, and sulfuric anhydride. Despite their hazardous nature, acid tars contain components that are essential in the production of bituminous materials. Additionally, acid tars are considered secondary material resources and are therefore more cost-effective compared to other raw materials. Proper processing of acid tars can lead to the recovery of valuable products while minimizing the negative impact on the environment. Despite the reduction in the use of sulfuric acid for the purification of oils and paraffins and the cessation of its use for the purification of kerosenes and gasoline, the amount of sulfuric acid waste is very significant. Current production acid tar containing sulfuric acid is a very unstable product. During storage, reactions of sulfonation, polymerization, polycondensation, etc. occur in it. Acid tars in storage ponds differ significantly in their chemical composition from acid tars of the current production. In addition, due to acid leaching by atmospheric and groundwater, the acid number of pond tar is significantly lower than that of the original (fresh) acid tar.

During storage, due to the impact of atmospheric precipitation (snow, rain), the contents of storage ponds are divided into three layers: the upper one is acid oil (light oil part of acid tar), at the moment this layer has been exhausted; medium - acidic water, consisting of atmospheric precipitation, sulfuric acid and acid sulfonated tars, this layer is sent for neutralization to the factory water treatment system; lower - bottom acid sludge (pasty state) and sulfuric acid, currently not disposed of.

The physicochemical characteristics and height of each of the layers are different and are determined by the time of filling, the place and depth of sampling. Pond acid tars are a fairly stable product. In their physical and chemical composition, they differ significantly from the acid tars of the current production, since the presence of atmospheric oxygen and free sulfuric acid contributes to the complex processes of oxidation and

polymerization in their organic part. In addition, prolonged sedimentation of acid in ponds and interaction with rainfall affects the composition of the acidic part of acid tars, that is, the acid number of acid tars in the current production is much higher than the acid number of pond acid tar.

The composition of acid tars (AT) includes a large number of various sulfonated compounds, some of which have been studied. [3]

The primary reaction products are sulfonic acids, acidic and medium esters. Aliphatic, naphthenic, aromatic and their polycondensed derivatives can be used as radicals. Sulfonic acids and acid esters are also reactive, therefore, as secondary products, there can be compounds formed during their interaction with both the original and newly obtained substances. Acid esters are soluble in water, they are easily hydrolyzed to form the corresponding alcohols and acids. Medium esters are colorless oily liquids, insoluble in water, but readily soluble in organic substances. Chemical reactions occurring in acid sludge lead to the formation of resinous high molecular weight products containing sulfur and oxygen. Oxygen-containing compounds can be carboxylic acids (naphthenic, asphaltogenic) that entered the tar from oil or formed during the oxidation of paraffins and naphthenes. The interaction of these acids with sulfuric acid or oleum leads to the formation of mixed sulfocarboxylic acids.

Depending on the origin, acid tars can be divided into:

- acid tars from the purification of straight run light distillates;
- acid tars from the purification of cracked gasolines;
- acid tars from the purification of petroleum products with fuming sulfuric acid or gaseous sulfuric anhydride;
- acid tars from the purification of lubricating oils (medical, aviation, perfumery, refrigeration, etc.).

Main Part

The study aimed to develop a more sustainable and efficient method for utilizing acid tars as a secondary material resource by using an electrochemical approach. The process involves the use of an electrochemical cell to break down the acid tar into its constituent parts, which can then be separated and purified to obtain bituminous materials. The study also looked at the kinetics of the neutralization and oxidation processes of acid tar under the influence of an electric current.

Theoretical provisions and technological solutions were developed for the process, which involved mixing the acid tar with a suitable electrolyte and introducing it into the anode compartment of an electrochemical cell. A current was passed through the cell, causing the acid tar to undergo electrolysis, resulting in the production of hydrogen gas and a mixture of bituminous materials and other by-products.

The study provides valuable insights into the use of an electrochemical approach for the utilization of acid tars, which can contribute to a more sustainable and efficient use of this secondary material resource.

The findings of this study could be useful for the development of industrial-scale processes for the production of bituminous materials from acid tars.

Getting bituminous material from acid tar is associated with a number of difficulties, both in terms of technological design and hardware design. Based on the literature data and the conducted experiments, the process of acid tar heating was characterized by high energy consumption and duration. Since it was carried out by heat-electric heaters (HEH), built into the interior of the container containing it. Due to the low heat transfer, the mass of acid tar is heated for a long time from the surface of the heating elements to the inner surface of the tank, which significantly lengthens the heating operation to achieve the required temperature and viscosity of the raw material for transfer to the subsequent operation. This process is accompanied by coking of the product, which in turn leads to certain difficulties in the operation of the equipment. Based on the obtained classification of acid tars with different storage periods, it can be concluded that, despite the fact that acid tar from storage ponds has an acid value of 60-50 mg KOH / g of tar, it is an electrically conductive medium; therefore, it is proposed by using the electrical conductivity of acid tar and placing electrodes in the reactor, as well as the exclusion of the addition of a neutralizing agent and the heating of acid tar, neutralization, oxidation and modification of the resulting bituminous binder, to be carried out in one apparatus, while it is possible to obtain bituminous materials with indicators approaching the requirements of bituminous material for bituminous material. This process is accompanied by intense evolution of hydrogen, which plays the role of a floating gas.

Hydrogen evolution is a multi-stage process, including the following stages: transportation of water molecules (the content of which in acid tar is up to 40%) or hydroxonium ions H_3O^+ to the cathode surface; transformation of the H_3O^+ ion into a hydrogen atom adsorbed on the metal surface:

The formation of hydrogen molecules from hydrogen atoms adsorbed on the metal surface. Thus, due to the diffusion of hydrogen, the acid sludge is mixed, and due to the formation of OH groups, the acidic components are neutralized. Hydrogen, liberated at the cathode, probably performs several functions. Since a large number of reactions occur during various hydrogenation processes. As a rule, with an increase in temperature, hydrocracking reactions intensify, i.e., reactions in which C-C bonds are broken, for example, ring breaks, chain breaks; at the same time, C-H bonds are also broken, accompanied by the release of H_2 and aromatic hydrocarbons. [1-7]

In hydrogenation reactions, unsaturated hydrocarbons, formed as a result of the splitting of large molecules, add hydrogen and turn into saturated hydrocarbons. Dienes are the first to undergo hydrogenation.

Unsaturated compounds are saturated much more easily than aromatic compounds. Simultaneously, in the presence of atomic hydrogen in the system, along with cleavage and hydrogenation, isomerization, ring breaking and rearrangement, alkylation, hydrodealkylation, etc. occur. Studies have shown that the rearrangement and breaking of bonds in compounds proceeds with the formation of intermediate products, which in turn can be centers for the formation of asphaltenes in the resulting bituminous material (BM). To obtain bituminous material (BM) from Acid tar (AT), in our opinion, the most important reaction is the partial hydrogenation of polycyclic aromatic structures, followed by rupture of saturated rings and the formation of substituted monocyclic aromatic hydrocarbons [4-8, 12]. The side chains that appear as a result of such a break are easily cleaved off and, upon further saturation with atomic hydrogen, may be able to create new polycyclic structures.

Hydrogenation of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons can result in the formation of lighter aromatic, naphthenic, and paraffinic hydrocarbons. In particular, there is a high content of isostructural paraffinic hydrocarbons formed through a process known as hydrosomerization. Oxygen-containing organic compounds usually easily enter into hydrogenation reactions with the formation of the corresponding hydrocarbons and water [9-13]. The complex resinous and asphaltene substances of Acid tar (AT) contain a lot of oxygen, and therefore their conversion into hydrocarbon products is much more difficult. Of the oxygen-containing compounds, the most important are resins and asphaltenes, which, upon hydrogenation, are converted into lower molecular weight hydrocarbons and water. That complicates the process of oxidation and formation of a more solid structure of bituminous material (BM). But these intermediate products containing highly active molecules are usually easily destroyed during hydrogenation, while the intensity of hydrogen evolution at the cathode can be controlled by increasing the voltage in the system, reducing the distance between the electrodes, or increasing the surface of the electrodes. In this process, a partial destruction of mainly oxygen compounds occurs. [13-15]

Decomposition products are saturated with hydrogen to form water and saturated or aromatic hydrocarbons. During electrochemical oxidation, anodic processes are characterized by intense release of atomic oxygen, which is the strongest oxidizing agent, which accelerates the process of converting acid tar into bituminous material (BM) compared to air oxidation.

Reactions involving atoms and radicals proceed much faster than molecular reactions, this can be seen by comparing, for example, the monomolecular decomposition of a molecule and a free radical similar in structure: propane and n-propyl radical:

The first reaction proceeds with a rate constant:
 $k = 4 \times 10^{17} \exp(-343/RT) = 6 \times 10^{19} \text{ c}^{-1}$ at 500 K, and the second

$$ck = 5 \times 10^{11} \exp(-106/RT) = 4\text{c}^{-1}$$

Such a huge difference in the rate constants (19 orders of magnitude) is due to the fact that during the decay of the n propyl radical, the breakage of the C-C bond is compensated by the formation of the p-C-C bond (bond strength 240 kJ / mol), and there is no such compensation during the decay of propane. In turn, the formation of the p-C-C-bond is predetermined by the presence of an unpaired electron in the propyl radical, which takes part in the formation of a double bond when the C-C-bond is broken. A similar situation is observed if we compare the decomposition of an alcohol and an alkoxy radical, an aldehyde and an acyl radical, etc.

Let us compare the reactions of abstraction of the H atom by atomic and molecular oxygen:

$$\begin{aligned} k, \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ c}^{-1} (300\text{K}) \lg A \text{ E, kC/mol } D_H \\ \text{O} &5.6 \times 10^7 \quad 10.12 \quad 13.6 \quad -22 \\ \text{O}_2 &5.7 \times 10^{17} \quad 12.90 \quad 16.9 \quad -167 \end{aligned}$$

And in this example, we see a huge difference in the activity of an atom and a molecule.

Let's compare the thermodynamic characteristics of these two particles:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{DG (300K) } D_H, \text{ kC/mol } D_S, \text{ kC/mol} \\ \text{O}_2 &-61.5 \quad 0 \quad 205 \\ \text{O} &200.7 \quad 249 \quad 161 \end{aligned}$$

It can be seen that O and O₂ differ in the BO value, and this difference stems from the difference in the enthalpies of formation of particles. The oxygen atom carries a large amount of chemical energy, which is manifested in the abstraction reaction: in the case of O₂, this reaction is endothermic, and in the case of O, it is exothermic. Hence such a large difference in activation energies and rate constants. Consequently, the high chemical activity of atoms and radicals is due to the fact that they are particles in which chemical energy is stored in the form of an unsaturated free valency. Therefore, the electrochemical oxidation of acid tar with atomic oxygen proceeds very intensively. At the same time, the highest rate of oxidation takes place while maintaining a certain electrolyte concentration. In this case, there is a more intensive formation of associates, that is, the content of resins in the acid tar decreases, but the content of asphaltenes increases. At the same time, the viscosity of the system increases, that is, there is an intensive oxidation of the tar in the bituminous material. During the experiment, it was noticed that several factors have a significant impact on the speed of the process: the distance between the electrodes, the material from which the electrodes are made, the applied voltage and modifying additives.

The process of obtaining bituminous material from acid tar by the electrochemical method was carried out using alternating current. Thus, when a voltage of 50–70 V was applied to the electrodes, the current in the system was 12–45 A, while the distance between the electrodes was 5–7 cm, and the process temperature was 70–98°C. It is noted that the process is very intensive and within 35–40 minutes it is possible to obtain

bituminous material (BM) in terms of its indicators approaching the requirements of specifications for bituminous material (BM) from Acid tar (AT). The neutralization process was monitored by the change in the electrical conductivity of EG, its resistivity, and the change in acid number by potentiometric titration. Based on the presented graphs, a sharp drop in current in the system is noticeable, which indicates that at the

end of the process, the electrolyte content sharply decreases. This is confirmed by an increase in resistivity (from $0.97 \cdot 10^2$ to $1.5 \cdot 10^9 \text{ Om /m}^2$), As well as a sharp drop in electrical conductivity (from 14 mCm /cm to 0.1 mCm /cm), that is, it can be concluded that the electrochemical neutralization process is successful.

At the same time, the acid number of acid tar dropped from 58.5 to 2.1 mg KOH/g tar. All research data are presented in the graphs.

Figure 1

The dependence of the change in the current strength in the system during the production of bituminous material (BM) by the electrochemical method.

As mentioned earlier, the oxidation of Acid tar (AT) in BM bituminous material (BM) by the electrochemical method occurs due to the intensive formation of atomic oxygen at the anode. In acid solutions, where

the content of OH⁻ ions is low and does not provide the necessary rate of anodic oxygen formation, water molecules are subjected to discharge:

In solutions of oxygen-containing acids, acid anions can probably take a direct part in the reaction of oxygen evolution. In the case of sulfuric acid, it may be direct.

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Oxygen is released here as a result of the discharge of sulfate ions, possibly by the reaction:

Since, in the reaction of the electrolytic formation of oxygen, not two are involved, as in the reaction of hydrogen evolution, but four electrons. This leads to the appearance of several electrochemical stages, each of which can determine the rate of the entire anodic process. A change in the composition of the electrolyte can affect the kinetics of oxygen evolution and the properties of the resulting substances. By changing the current strength, the voltage in the system, it is likely that it will be possible to obtain complex organic molecules of a given structure, since in addition to the stages occurring at the electrode-electrolyte phase boundary, purely chemical transformations that occur in the electrolyte under the influence of elevated temperature can also be of significant importance. The transfer of the reaction from the electrode surface into the interior of the electrolyte can be carried out not only with the help of any

additives, but also by its participants themselves - free radicals and other active particles that can initiate the development of a chain transformation. In the course of the electrooxidation reaction, intermediate compounds can probably appear, which play the role of autocatalysts of the process. As a result of the electrochemical oxidation process, the group composition of acid tar and the resulting bituminous binder based on it was analyzed by gas-liquid chromatography.

The study of changes in the components of the resulting material and raw materials was carried out by the method of IR - spectroscopy. It has been established that the mass fraction of maltenes in Acid tar (AT) is 58 wt. %. During the oxidation of Acid tar (AT) to obtain bituminous material (BM), the content of maltenes decreased to 50%, and the mass fraction of asphaltenes increased. If in the original Acid tar (AT) the content of asphaltenes is 8–9 wt %, then in the corresponding bituminous material (BM) it is more than 25 wt %, which is also confirmed by chromatographic analysis[11].

Table 1

Component	Asphaltenes,%	Resins,%	Total	PNU	MTSA	BTSA	PTSA
acid tar	8-9	34-40	58-51	52-48	3-2	2-1	1,0
Acid tar bitumen	>25	>19	>50	>46	>1	>2	>3

Acid tar (AT) and bituminous material (BM) based on it, obtained by the electrochemical method, was separated into separate fractions according to a method based on the precipitation of the solid part (asphaltenes) from a benzene solution of tar and bituminous material (BM), followed by the separation of asphaltene from maltenes. All fractions of tar and bituminous material (BM) were studied in the ultraviolet region of the spectrum. The work was carried out on a KFK-72 spectrophotometer, the thickness of the analyzed layer was 1 cm and 0.02 cm, solvents: 1-propyl alcohol, hexane, acetonitrile. The electronic spectra of monocyclic aromatic compounds are characterized by a-, p- and p-bands, characteristic of substituted benzene. This is evidenced by the similarity of the bands in position, nature and intensity. Otherwise, the spectrum of the fraction of bicyclic aromatic compounds is prescribed. The benzene absorption bands (a, p, and P) are strongly redshifted. The P-band is clearly visible in the spectrum, has a wavelength of 222 nm, k=58. p-band of benzene absorption relative to the p-band of monocyclic aromatic compounds is shifted by 34 nm and has X=262 nm, k=48. The long-wavelength a-band in the

spectrum is visible as a shoulder on the long-wavelength decay of the p-band (A, = 290 nm, k = 23).

A strong shift in the absorption bands of bicyclic aromatic hydrocarbons indicates the presence in them of condensed benzene nuclei, which, probably, can be naphthalene derivatives. In polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, one could expect a high degree of condensation of benzene nuclei, i.e. the presence of cata or peri-condensed compounds. However, the absence of long-wavelength absorption bands indicates the absence of such compounds. The spectrum retains the benzene absorption bands of bicyclic aromatic compounds in the region of 295 and 260 nm, which are visible as shoulders on the long-wavelength decay of the band. In addition, the spectrum of polycyclic aromatic compounds has a short wavelength band <208 nm, presumably of a monosubstituted benzene ring. Thus, the spectrum of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons is complex and is a superposition spectrum of one- and two-condensed benzene nuclei. Of particular interest are the spectra of resin and asphaltene fractions, since in the process of structuring bituminous material from acid tar, resins are the determining fraction. By the nature of the spectra and the location of the bands, the spectrum of acid tar

resins and acid tar bituminous material corresponds to the spectrum of monocyclic aromatic compounds.

The electronic spectra of bituminous material (BM) resins and asphaltenes do not have clear bands. They are smoothed and appear in the spectrum in the form of a plateau. The absorption bands of bituminous material (BM) fractions from Acid tar (AT) are shifted to the red region compared to the same Acid tar (AT) fractions. They have a smoothed character of the bands, the appearance of a short-wavelength band, apparently, also indicates the presence of mononuclear aromatic compounds in the nickel. Bands of polycyclic compounds are absent in the Acid tar (AT) spectra, as well as in the bituminous material (BM) spectra from Acid tar (AT). It is possible that there are similar compounds, but they are not the determining structures in the fractions of resins and asphaltenes of bituminous material from Acid tar (AT). With regard to macromolecular compounds and organic binders, as is known, two theories of their structure have been developed: micellar

and macromolecular. The micellar theory considers macromolecular compounds as a system of crystals (micelles). Each micelle consists of a significant number of small molecules connected to each other into one crystallite by association forces, while the association forces are so great that each micelle is an independent kinetic unit with a phase interface, i.e. qualitatively micellar structures can be considered as isolated phases. With regard to bitumen, this theory was developed by Nellenstein, who considers bitumen as a colloidal system, where the phase is asphaltenes surrounded by a shell of resins in an oily environment. A bituminous micelle is a complex system of various substances from an asphaltene core, more or less strongly associated with resins of different molecular weights, to oils, which are a dispersed medium.

In the resulting solid bituminous binders from acid tar, where micelles occupy most of the system, the oils are in a bound immobile state due to solvation.

Figure 5: and UV spectra of acid tar: 1 - BCA; 2 - MCA; 3 - OCA. b. UV spectra of resin and asphaltene fractions: Acid tar (AT): 1 - resin; 2 - asphaltenes; bituminous material (BM) from Acid tar (AT): 3 - resins; 4 - asphaltenes

Figure 6: IR HPLC chromatogram a) Acid tar (AT); b) BMiz Acid tar (AT) (2-3 min. retention - sulfonic acids; 4-6 min. - oils and resins; 6-8 min. asphaltenes; b) IR spectrum of Acid tar (AT) (1) and bituminous material (BM) (2) based on it.

In a more plastic product, with a lower viscosity, the micelles are not bound to each other and can freely mix in the oils. Depending on the content and properties of the components of the resulting bituminous binders (oils, resins, asphaltenes), various disperse structures can form: sol, gel, sol-gel with certain physics-mechanical properties. Macromolecular theory considers high-molecular organic substances as compounds of chain or

branched macromolecules, which can represent chains of various structures: linear, branched and spatially built. Macromolecules continuously change their position and configuration, as a result of which they take on various forms. The properties of macromolecular compounds depend on the size of the molecular weight, the shape and its flexibility, the chemical structure and the magnitude of the forces of association. An increase in

molecular weight leads to an increase in intermolecular interaction, and, consequently, viscosity; the content of functional groups increases the rigidity of the chains. [13]

Hydrocarbons and heterogeneous derivatives that leave bituminous material (BM) from Acid tar (AT), depending on the structure, the content of active functional groups, are in different and intermolecular interactions and have different deformability (flexibility) of molecules, which determines the structural and mechanical properties of bituminous material (BM). As applied to bituminous material (BM) from Acid tar (AT), both according to micellar and macromolecular theory, the main structure-forming component of bituminous material (BM) is asphaltenes. If micelles are considered as associates of asphaltenes held by van der Waals forces, in which there is no contact of a substance with a clearly pronounced difference in properties, then there is no fundamental difference between the two approaches in explaining the structure of organic binders. Based on this, the structure of the sol can be identified with the structure of the solution, the gel - with a structured disperse system (micelles or macromolecules), the sol-gel is an intermediate structure.

CONCLUSION

Research on the group composition of Acid tar (AT) and electrochemically oxidized bituminous material (BM) derived from it indicates that Acid tar (AT) has a sol-like structure with a reduced content of asphaltenes (8-10%) and a predominant amount of oils (up to 58%). The resulting bituminous material (BM) from Acid tar (AT) has a gel-like structure and is similar to dispersed systems with an increased content of asphaltenes (more than 25%) and a smaller amount of resins (up to 19%). The structure of the BM is characterized by the formation of a coagulation network or a framework, which consists of a high-molecular part of asphaltenes (macromolecules with a weight of more than 1000) or their associates (micelles) in the medium of oils (molecular weight 300-500) with a reduced content of resins (molecular weight 500-1000). The results of IR spectroscopy allow us to conclude that in bituminous material (BM) from Acid tar (AT) there is a densification and isomerization of the structure of the resulting material. The band at 1377 cm⁻¹, reflecting the content of C-H bonds of methyl groups, and the band at 1458 cm⁻¹, belonging to the C-H bonds of methylene groups, were used for analysis. The ratio of signal intensities in these bands in Acid tar (AT) and bituminous material (BM) based on it is 0.43 and 0.5 relative units, i.e., the content of aromatic structures increased in the process of tar oxidation.

In simpler terms, the stability of the coagulated structure formed by asphaltenes in bituminous material depends not only on the concentration of asphaltenes, but also on the degree of chemical affinity between asphaltenes and the other components of the material. This affinity is measured by the lyophobicity index L, which is the difference in aromaticity between the asphaltenes and the oils in the material. The presence of aromatic systems in heavy oil residues is important for

their ability to form the coagulated structure seen in bituminous materials.

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